

Developing metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen science impacts on the environment and society

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1 Intro

1.1 Background on MICS

The MICS project develops approaches and tools to evaluate citizen-science impacts. These approaches and tools can help to plan and implement projects in ways that lead to more robust results.

The MICS project specifically aims to:

- provide comprehensive, participatory and inclusive metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen science impacts;
- implement an impact-assessment knowledge-base through toolboxes for methods application, information visualisation, and delivery to decision makers, citizens and researchers;
- improve the effectiveness of nature-based solutions through test-site development and citizen-science tool validation;
- generate new approaches that strengthen the role of citizen science in supporting research and development;
- foster a citizen-science approach to increase the extent to which scientific evidence is taken up by policy makers through recommendations and guidelines.

The result is an integrated platform where these metrics and instruments are available for use by anyone involved in a citizen-science project wanting to understand its impact, whether at the planning stage or several years after the project's conclusion. This platform is validated by pilot testing in four test and validation sites across Europe. These sites explore the applicability of MICS impact-assessment tools in regions with differing needs, contexts, and approaches to nature-based solutions, and with various levels of citizen-science application. For example, in Western Europe, river restoration is increasingly carried out within an ecosystem-based management framework at river or catchment scale; in Southern Europe, river restoration tends to be issue-specific with some ecosystem relevance; in Central and Eastern Europe, river restoration is about ecosystem protection and related to existing infrastructure. The four test and validation sites selected are in the UK, Italy, Hungary and Romania.

1.2 Purpose and scope of this report

This report is a deliverable of Work Package 4 (WP4) – 'Test-site development and tool validation'. The purpose of this report is to provide the guidance for co-designing and enhancing hands-on citizen-science activities in the MICS case-study sites, using an adapted version of the Ground Truth 2.0 co-design methodology. It is structured as a compendium, providing instructions for the co-design process as well as dedicated structures to capture the results of the activities.

2 Methodology for co-designing hands-on citizen science in the MICS case-study sites

The MICS project is developing an integrated platform of metrics and instruments to measure the impacts of [citizen science](#). Four case study sites (in the UK, Italy, Hungary and Romania) explore the co-creation of citizen science in regions with differing needs, contexts, and approaches to environmental management (for example, river restoration), and with various levels of citizen science application. The project adopts the definition of *nature-based solutions* (NBSs) by the *International Union for Conservation of Nature* (IUCN): NBS are ...“*actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits*”. The MICS case-study sites represent different types and stages of NBS implementation, with some activities merely planned, others already implemented.

Setting up and implementing hands-on citizen science activities in the four case-study sites to evaluate the impact of citizen science requires a sound approach. The **Ground Truth 2.0 co-design methodology** (Wehn and Pfeiffer, 2020) represents best practice in the co-design of hands-on citizen science and is particularly suitable for the context of NBS due to the methodology’s focus on generating citizen science activities that are purpose-driven to address jointly agreed societal challenges, based on a sound understanding of the social context.

For the co-design of hands-on citizen science activities in the four case studies, MICS adopts and adapts the best practice generated by the Ground Truth 2.0 (GT2.0) project, adapting this approach from full-scale citizen observatories in Ground Truth 2.0 to purpose-driven citizen science activities in MICS. This adapted version will therefore serve to guide the implementation of the citizen science activities in the four MICS case-study sites. Its challenge-driven approach will ensure that the MICS citizen Science activities are ‘co-designed for impact’. The comparison of its implementation in the four case study sites will result in clear recommendations for those involved in citizen science projects. Moreover, the resulting insights from the application of the co-design methodology as well as the MICS metrics and instruments for measuring the impacts of citizen science will be used to refine the MICS platform toolbox and to generate clear recommendations for those involved in citizen science projects.

This deliverable draws on key deliverables of the Ground Truth 2.0 project, namely the overall co-design methodology (Wehn and Pfeiffer, 2020) as well as guidance for stakeholder and context analysis (Pfeiffer et al., 2018), stakeholder engagement (Anema et al., 2018) and functional design (Alfonso et al., 2018).

2.1 Guiding principles for the co-design of Citizen Science in MICS

i. Citizen participation in the Scientific Method

The GT2.0 co-design methodology stipulates that, in principle, citizens can participate in any stage of the scientific method:

- *Framing of the research question*
- *Research design*
- *Data collection*
- *Data analysis and interpretation*
- *Understanding results*
- *Publication/management action*

ii. Relevant stakeholders

Citizen Science involves at the very least two types of stakeholders: *citizens* (i.e. non-experts) and *scientists*. In order to fully capture the potential of Citizen Science in terms of knowledge co-creation in applied settings, the GT2.0 co-design methodology stipulates a diverse range of stakeholders should be involved in the co-design process as early as possible, namely:

- *citizens, communities and civil society organisations*
- *scientists*
- *public sector actors - legislative (policy makers)*
- *public sector actors - executive (local authorities; implementing agencies)*
- *industry/private sector*

The GT2.0 co-design methodology further postulates that no single stakeholder (pre)defines the challenge that the Citizen Science activities will address. Nevertheless, the specific roles of the stakeholders involved in the citizen science co-design process may differ according to cultural contexts and the co-design dynamics can be adjusted accordingly.

iii. LivingLab principles

The GT2.0 co-design methodology stipulates that all co-design activities embody the guiding principles of the Living Lab methodology¹, namely that the citizen science co-design process:

- *Creates **value** for users by understanding their needs and motivations*
- *Gives future users **influence** on the decisions*
- *Aims for **sustainability** in economic, environmental and social terms*
- *Involves multiple perspectives and collaborates widely for **openness***
- *Carries out activities in the **real-life context***

iv. Open-source tools and existing tools of MICS partners

The citizen science activities in the MICS case-study sites will use open source citizen science tools (e.g., Epicollect5 [<https://five.epicollect.net/>], Open Data Kit [<https://opendatakit.org/>]) and existing tools of the MICS partners (e.g., Freshwater Watch), provided that these serve the citizen science requirements identified and agreed upon in the citizen science co-design process.

2.2 The adapted co-design methodology in a nutshell

The adapted GT2.0 co-design methodology consists of the following seven stages:

- Stage 1: Getting started: rapid screening
- Stage 2: Tailor methods to context
- Stage 3: Initiate co-design group & capture requirements
- Stage 4: Technical review & citizen science tool set-up
- Stage 5: Plan & launch citizen science activities
- Stage 6: Analysis, outreach & triggering change
- Stage 7: Conclude OR Enhance & sustain citizen science tools and activities

Several of these stages consist of carefully designed social interaction moments with relevant stakeholders who co-design the citizen science activities in order to generate new knowledge, insights and (if desired) follow-up actions to address the jointly agreed societal challenge. Iterations of distinct

¹ Ståhlbröst, A. and M. Holst (n.d.) The Living Lab Methodology Handbook, University of Technology and Centre for Distance-spanning Technology, Sweden [https://www.ltu.se/cms_fs/1.101555!/file/LivingLabsMethodologyBook_web.pdf].

stages and stakeholder interactions may be necessary on a case-by-case basis to ensure stage-specific objectives are met.

Figure 1: The seven steps of the adapted Ground Truth 2.0 co-design methodology (Source: Wehn, 2019)

2.3 Co-design compendium for each MICS case study

The remainder of this report contains the structure of the co-design compendium that will be set up for each MICS case study. The co-design compendium contains the guidance for the ‘journey’ of the MICS case studies through each stage of the adapted co-design methodology.

This compendium is a collection of instructions, work sheets and guidelines, based on the adapted GT2.0 co-design methodology, for the MICS case studies. The respective compendium of each case is also a workspace for the MICS case studies.

The MICS process to work with the co-design compendium is as follows:

1. T4.1 Task leader IHE Delft prepares instructions on the GT2.0 co-design methodology for the MICS case studies, which are the same for all case studies and collated in this compendium template.
2. MICS case study leads use their respective compendium to report all results of their citizen science co-design and citizen science implementation activities, filling in the document over time. This ensures all information is easily accessible for all tasks in MICS, without the need for much coordination.
3. The progressive completion of the compendium [i.e. completion of fields in the main text and in the Annexes, as requested] feeds into and is undertaken during the regular case study team teleconferences and discussions. Short tables are included in the main sections, whereas long and expanding tables are included in Annexes.

The compendium is structured according to the seven steps of the adapted co-design methodology for co-designing citizen science in the MICS case studies (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Co-designing Citizen Science in the MICS case studies

Each stage consists of a number of activities that need to be completed before advancing to the next stage. Iterations of activities may be necessary to ensure that stage-specific objectives are met. Next to the description of the detailed activities per stage, the guidance provided in this compendium includes the overarching objectives of each stage together with measure(s) of whether the objectives have been reached.

The compendium also contains guidance for the following continuous activities:

1. **Stakeholder engagement** including the drafting of specific messages and activities to recruit, moderate and motivate stakeholders, based on an initial and evolving stakeholder analysis as well as continuous use of stakeholder management tools.
2. **Stakeholder workshops** as key modalities for the user-centred co-design of the Citizen Science activities, including the collection and documentation of user requirements in preparation of the functional design of the citizen science tools, as well as part of the implementation of the co-designed citizen science activities.
3. **Observation of activities** 1 and 2 above and documentation of relevant insights in a logbook (one per workshop/event), to feed into monitoring & evaluation efforts, in order to judge overall progress, success and evolving impacts of the activities.
4. **Monitoring & evaluation** of MICS case study progress through the citizen science co-design process and implementation of citizen science activities and to capture lessons learned from the application of the adapted Ground Truth 2.0 co-design methodology.

*The overarching task for the **case study Leaders** in this citizen science co-design process is to manage, on the one hand, the team of MICS case study partners and, on the other, to make sure that all contributing stakeholders are kept informed and engaged during the initial co-design as well as the eventual implementation of citizen science activities.*

3 Stage 1: Getting started: rapid screening

Main objective of stage 1:

- Appointment of MICS team members for citizen science co-design
- Summarise the context for the Citizen Science activities related to NBS in the MICS case study area
- Ambition of citizen science for NBS in this case study agreed by the MICS team members
- Background and context information gathered for the formation of the co-design group of relevant stakeholders
- Sound set up of stakeholder management tools and procedures

Measure(s) of completion of stage 1:

- Summary of NBS case study description completed
- List of 15-20 stakeholders who will be invited to participate in the co-design process identified and invited
- Stakeholder management tool in Annex 2 completed with initial stakeholder details
- Statement regarding MICS staff compliance with procedures for stakeholder data

Checklist of Actions to be completed during this stage (for instructions, see sections below)

Action	Done
ACTION 1: Indicate the appointment of MICS team members for your case study in Table 1.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 2: Insert your MICS NBS case study information as per MICS template on the project SharePoint.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 3: Discuss and agree on the ambition of the Citizen Science activities in the MICS case studies in relation to the local NBS. Please capture the result of your discussion in Table 2 below.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 4: Discuss and agree on the planned timing of your MICS case study per stage of the co-design methodology for your case study and capture the result of your discussion in Annex 1.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 5: Complete Table 3 for your case study.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 6: For each stakeholder identified in Table 3, include detailed contact information in the Stakeholder Management table in Annex 2 and confirm your compliance with the MICS ethics and data management procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/>

3.1 MICS team members

Co-designing the citizen science activities in the MICS case studies is a team effort of several MICS partners and their staff members. In order for your team to work well together, there needs to be clarity about the appointment of specific MICS staff members to distinct roles in the MICS case study, who to invite to the regular case-study site teleconferences, etc.

ACTION 1: Indicate the appointment of MICS team members for your case study in Table 1. If there is staff turnover during the lifetime of the MICS project (2019-2021), please update this table accordingly.

Table 1: MICS team members for this case-study site

Role	MICS team member	Back up contact
Case-study site lead		
Guidance on citizen science co-design (IHE)		
Guidance on citizen science hands-on activities (Earthwatch)		
WP4 lead		

3.2 NBS summary

It is important to capture the context in which the citizen science activities are to be embedded. In MICS, this relates primarily to the NBS-related activities in the case study.

ACTION 2: <Insert here your MICS NBS case study information as [per MICS template](#) on the project SharePoint>

3.3 Ambition of Citizen Science for NBS in this case study agreed by the MICS team members

The MICS case studies are supposed to undertake hands-on Citizen Science activities in their respective case study areas, linked to the NBS in the case. Each case study has its particularities, including the type and maturity of the NBS in the case study area, as is to be detailed in the section above.

While the co-design process provides the means to obtain substantive inputs from a wide range of relevant stakeholders, it is important that the MICS partners involved in your case study have a joint understanding and agreement on the ambition of the citizen science activities from a project perspective, especially how they are intended to relate to the NBS of your case study. This alignment will ensure you are working towards a common goal.

ACTION 3: Please discuss and agree on the ambition of the Citizen Science activities in the MICS case studies in relation to the local NBS. Please capture the result of your discussion in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Ambition of citizen science for NBS in this case study agreed by the MICS partners

Ambition of citizen science for NBS in this case study (short version)	Explanation of agreed citizen science ambition

The MICS Impact Assessment Framework developed by WP2 will assess the evolving impacts of the MICS case studies as a distinct effort, with instructions for the case studies outside this compendium.

As part of scoping the ambition of your case study, it is important to define the envisaged timing and Key Performance Indicators to measure progress. This will provide continuous means for monitoring & evaluation of your case study in terms of progress through the citizen science co-design process and implementation of citizen science activities.

ACTION 4: Please discuss and agree on the planned timing of your MICS case study per stage of the co-design methodology for your case study and capture the result of your discussion in Annex 1.

These stated ambitions should be reviewed regularly during the MICS case study team teleconferences (at least once a month).

3.4 Stakeholder identification for the co-design process

The specific challenge for which the citizen science activities will co-create knowledge and insights will be identified and agreed upon during the co-design process. This is different from the ambition agreed upon in the section above, which indicates the overall role of the citizen science activities in the MICS case study related to NBS.

The co-design methodology stipulates that **no single stakeholder fully (pre)defines the specific challenge that the Citizen Science activities will address** (see guiding principles ii and iii in section 2.1). A diverse range of stakeholders needs to be involved in the co-design process in order to fully capture the knowledge co-creation potential of Citizen Science. In the context of citizen science for NBS, these are:

- *citizens, communities and/or civil society organisations*
- *scientists*
- *public sector actors - legislative (policy makers)*
- *public sector actor - executive (local authorities, river basin organisations, implementing agencies)*
- *industry/private sector*
- *other (outside the above categories)*

User-centred co-design of Citizen Science involves working with a *core* group of stakeholders. In the Ground Truth 2.0 methodology, this core group which jointly designs the Citizen Science activities is called the citizen science **co-design group**. This co-design group consists of carefully selected persons (15-20) representing the stakeholder groups listed above, who are motivated to contribute to the design and set-up of the Citizen Science activities.

Moreover, the citizen science co-design process builds on existing communities (e.g. in the case of MICS, related to NBS) while also creating a distinct community of stakeholders related to the Citizen Science activities.

ACTION 5: Please complete Table 3 below for your case study.

Given the context in MICS of setting up Citizen Science activities related to the NBS in each case study, the list of identified stakeholders for the citizen science co-design group is likely to be very closely linked/overlapping with existing NBS-related stakeholder groups. If you identify a relevant stakeholder who does not fit in any of the pre-defined four categories, please include this in the category 'other' and provide details.

While some categories have a natural limit in terms of the max. number of persons you can identify (e.g. RBO representatives), others such as citizens provide the opportunity to diversify and to substantiate the group, especially in view of potential drop out during the citizen science co-design process.

Note: In stage 3 of the co-design process, once the core challenge to be addressed by the Citizen Science activities has been agreed upon, a stakeholder analysis is undertaken in order to identify which additional stakeholders need to be involved or consulted. For example, depending on the selected challenge, additional scientists may need to be included who are experts in relevant fields.

Table 3: Stakeholders to be involved in the citizen science co-design group in this case study

Stakeholder type	Name & organisation
Citizens	
Scientists	
Public sector actors – legislative (policy makers)	
Public sector actors - executive (local authorities; RBO; implementing agencies)	
Industry/Private sector	
Other (case-specific):	

3.5 Stakeholder data management

Over the course of the next few months, you will identify, contact and interact with a wide range of stakeholders for the case study. To keep track of the preparations and interactions, and to communicate the activities within the MICS project for planning and research purposes, it is essential to collect stakeholder information in the master list in **Annex 2**.

- *Names and contact details*
- *Stakeholder classification acc. to GT2.0 methodology*
- *Status information*
- *Notes and remarks*

ACTION 6: For each stakeholder identified in Table 3, include detailed contact information in the Stakeholder Management table in Annex 2 and confirm your compliance with the MICS ethics and data management procedures in the box below.

Note: the collection of personal data is subject to ethics requirements, the data management has to comply with [MICS Ethics Deliverable D6.1 and D6.2 \(informed consent procedures that will be implemented in regard to the collection, storage and protection of personal data\)](#) and [MICS Deliverable D1.2 Project Management Handbook \(data management procedures\)](#).

Please confirm that staff with access to the stakeholder data contained in this compendium has been informed of the procedures outlined in MICS deliverable D6.1 (specifying when and how), and what measures have been taken to ensure compliance.

<write your case study response here>

We <insert name> confirm that staff with access to the stakeholder data contained in this compendium have been informed of the procedures outlined in DX.X (specifying when and how), and what measures have been taken to ensure compliance

4 Stage 2: Tailor interaction methods to context

Main objective of stage 2:

- Potential Co-design group invited
- Enabling environment authorities informed about the planned citizen science co-design process
- Understanding of cultural and local specificities for the citizen science co-design meetings

Measure(s) of completion of stage 2:

- Customized invitation message for each prospective citizen science co-design group member
- Completion of enabling environment briefing status
- Completion of conditions for citizen science co-design meetings

Checklist of Actions to be completed during this stage (for instructions, see sections below)

Action	Done
ACTION 7: Please complete Table 4 for each stakeholder type in your case study.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 8: Contact each stakeholder, using the tailored messages from Table 4, and include information about your engagement activities in the Stakeholder Management table (Annex 2).	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 9: Identify relevant Enabling Environment authorities and describe them in Table 5.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 10: Contact each identified relevant Enabling Environment authorities and include information about your outreach activities to them in the Stakeholder Management table (Annex 2).	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 11: Please complete Table 6 to capture the specific conditions for the co-design session in your case study.	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.1 Invitation to the citizen science co-design workshops

In this stage, the different key stakeholders identified for the citizen science co-design workshop day co-design workshop (see Stage 1, section 3.3, Table 3) need to be invited. This is typically done by reaching out to them via personal connections and communication (phone, email) and/or in bilateral meetings.

Stakeholders related to NBS are not equally powerful (e.g. due to their formal mandate) and different stakeholders are entitled to different consideration (e.g. due to their seniority). In order to ensure their commitment to the Citizen Science co-design process, it is important to relay their relevance for the process. This should be done via carefully tailored invitation messages for the above-mentioned communications.

These messages should address the following aspects:

- Why we are planning to undertake citizen science activities related to the case study's NBS and why we are co-designing them
- Why the input of stakeholder X is useful
- What stakeholder X gets out of it
- How stakeholder X can be involved

Here is an example from one of the Ground Truth 2.0 citizen observatories (Belgium), which started with the broad theme of improving the quality of life in Belgium:

Box 1: Example of tailored invitation for citizens to participate in the co-design process for a citizen observatory related to improving the quality of life in Belgium.

Why we are doing this:

We are aiming to generate better information about environmental aspects that impact on the quality of life in Belgium.

Why your input is useful:

Our ambition is to improve the knowledge of the local environment such as noise pollution. Each community has the best insight into these issues - you are the local experts.

What you are getting out of it:

Enabling citizens to share observations about their environment, we expect improved knowledge and insights into the local quality of life and problems. This can lead to targeted actions from politicians and administrations.

How you can be involved:

We are enabling everybody to participate using an online portal and apps and we will encourage their use via local media. You can help us design the most appropriate tools and approaches by participating in our co-design process.

ACTION 7: Please complete Table 4 for each stakeholder type in your case study.

Note: all recruitment activities have to comply with the MICS Ethics Deliverable 6.1 (procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants) and MICS Ethics Deliverable 6.2 (protection of personal data).

Table 4: Tailored messages for the prospective members of the citizen science co-design group in this case study

Stakeholder type	Tailored invitation message
Citizens	
Scientists	
Public sector actors – legislative (policy makers)	
Public sector actors (Implementing agencies; local authorities)	
Industry/Private sector	
Other (case-specific):	

ACTION 8: Contact each stakeholder, using the tailored messages from Table 4, and include information about your engagement activities in the Stakeholder Management table (Annex 2).

4.2 Reach out to enabling environment authorities

The enabling environment for NBS and citizen science consists of a wider range of authorities such as legislators and policy makers than those identified for participation in the citizen science co-design group (stage 1). Not all of these can of course be involved directly; nevertheless, it is important to inform relevant contacts among these stakeholders early on (and over time) of the planned citizen science co-design activities, so that they are aware and ideally supportive. Moreover, this group can consist of regulatory agencies relevant for the problem under investigation, entities relevant to solutions for the problem, and supporting organisations. For example, air quality is typically considered in the remit of a city administration, but solutions may have to involve regional road authorities and additional city units, whereas support can come from provincial government in the form of valuable insights and resources.

ACTION 9: Identify relevant Enabling Environment authorities and describe them in Table 5.

Table 5: Identified Enabling Environment authorities to keep informed

Enabling Environment authority (organisation)	Role / Reason to inform them about planned MICS citizen science co-design

ACTION 10: Contact each identified relevant Enabling Environment authority, tailoring your message to their responsibilities, and include information about your outreach activities to them in the Stakeholder Management table (Annex 2).

4.3 Tailoring the co-design workshops

The citizen science co-design process has to be tailored to this case study in terms of its local cultural setting, the history of stakeholder interactions, etc. The facilitation of the interactions within the workshop must be appropriate, and fit the context in which it takes place. This section therefore serves to identify the conditions for holding successful workshop-style/interactive meetings with the citizen science co-design group in your case study,

ACTION 11: Please complete Table 6 to capture the specific conditions for the citizen science co-design session in your case study.

Table 6: Conditions for holding workshop-style/interactive meetings with the citizen science co-design group in the case study

Key aspects	case study
Cultural specificities (e.g. language; extent to which general co-design	

principles can be applied here)	
Ways of interacting in meeting setting	
Opportunities for bringing these stakeholders together in the citizen science co-design process	
Challenges for bringing these stakeholders together in the citizen science co-design process	

5 Stage 3: Initiate co-design group & capture of requirements

Main objective of this stage:

- Develop a *common understanding* of the challenge to be addressed by Citizen Science activities (what new knowledge do we need?)
- Obtain a rich picture of the different stakeholders, i.e. their goals, practices, attitudes and values
- Arrive at *agreed objective(s)* for the Citizen Science activities (resulting in an agreement to act)
- Identify the *key requirements* (i.e. functionalities) aligned to those objectives

Measure(s) of completion of stage 3:

- One or more co-design workshop(s) held that serve to arrive at the challenge to be addressed as agreed by the citizen science co-design group
- Objectives for the citizen science activities agreed by the citizen science co-design group
- Theory of Change and its monitoring framework agreed
- Citizen Science activities defined (research questions and data collection details)

Checklist of Actions to be completed during this stage (for instructions, see sections below)

Action	Done
ACTION 12: Please address the items in the following 'to do' list and report progress during the regular case study team teleconferences.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 13: Following the completion of the citizen science co-design workshop(s), fill in the Logbook for this event jointly, immediately after the session. Include the results of the participants' online survey in the Logbook, once available.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 14: Following the completion of the citizen science co-design workshop(s), please fill in Table 7.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 15: Please complete the context analysis table in Annex 5.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 16: Please complete the stakeholder analysis table in Annex 6 and add any newly identified stakeholders in the Stakeholder Management table in Annex 2.	<input type="checkbox"/>

5.1 Practical aspects of the co-design workshop(s)

Depending on the stakeholders' preferences and availability, one or more citizen science co-design workshops will need to be held to generate the required agreements and insights into requirements. The structure of these workshops will be provided by IHE and jointly tailored among the MICS case study team. The preparations of these workshops require the completion of the following activities.

ACTION 12: Please address the items in the following 'to do' list and report progress during the regular case study team teleconferences.

Weeks before

1. Set the date & location and formally invite the stakeholders identified and approached bilaterally in stage 2
2. Clarify main facilitator/support roles among the MICS partners present to implement the workshop
3. Finalise the session design (provided by IHE) jointly in the case study team
4. Finalise the accompanying PPT slide set for the workshop (provided by IHE) and adjust it to the specific workshop setting (facilitator name, location, date, host event); adjust the activity instructions to be in line with the workshop setting and the session design

Days before

1. Prepare print outs of the MICS informed consent sheet (see Ethics Deliverables), tailored to the workshop setting (date and data manager)
2. Have post its, markers and other supporting material ready
3. Pack the MICS banner and set it up in the room before the workshop starts
4. Set up the room with for groups of 3-4 people (max) per table

After the Workshop

1. Take photos of all materials produced during the workshop (post its, compass posters, etc.)
2. Gather all physical workshop material post its, compass posters, etc. and keep it safe
3. Hold a de-briefing session (ideally on the same day) with the MICS team to complete the Logbook for this event (see Evaluation section).
4. Digitise all workshop material (write up post its, etc.) and include it in the relevant sections of this citizen science co-design compendium.

5.2 Evaluation of the co-design workshop(s)

Each citizen science co-design event needs to be evaluated in two ways **on site, at the end of the meeting**:

- By the participants by means of an online survey (prepared by IHE)
- By the MICS team facilitating the event by means of a de-briefing session, jointly completing the Logbook for this event (using the format provided in **Annex 3**).

ACTION 13: Following the completion of the citizen science co-design workshop(s), fill in the Logbook for this event jointly, immediately after the session. Include the results of the participants’ online survey in the Logbook, once available.

5.3 Documentation of co-design workshop(s)

This sections captures the following outputs of the co-design workshop(s):

- Challenge to be addressed by the citizen science activities
- CS objective(s)
- Research question(s)
- User stories

ACTION 14: Following the completion of the citizen science co-design workshop(s), please fill in Table 7.

Table 7: Citizen science co-design outputs

<i>Item</i>	<i>Details</i>
<i>Agreed challenge for the Citizen Science activities related to NBS in your case study</i>	
<i>Identified leverage points - What aspects can be influenced, by whom, how?</i>	
<i>Agreed objective(s) for the citizen science</i>	

Activities in your case study	
Agreed research question(s) for the citizen science activities	

5.4 Context analysis and Stakeholder analysis

Now that the core challenge to be addressed by the Citizen Science activities has been agreed upon, a context analysis and a stakeholder analysis have to be undertaken.

The Context Analysis serves to understand political and societal forces that might affect the case study Cases, ensure that the citizen science approach is appropriate, embedded and effective for the situation, and provide insights useful for planning an engagement and communication strategy.

A stakeholder analysis has to be undertaken in order to identify which additional stakeholders need to be involved or consulted, if any. Specific guidance for completing the stakeholder analysis will be provided by IHE during the case study team teleconferences.

ACTION 15: Please complete the context analysis table in Annex 5.

ACTION 16: Please complete the stakeholder analysis table in Annex 6 and add any newly identified stakeholders in the Stakeholder Management table in Annex 2.

5.5 Analysis of citizen science co-design session results

Following the co-design workshop(s), the context analysis and the stakeholder analysis, the results are analysed in a collaborative session of the case study team. This section will summarise the functional design of the citizen science activities to inform the technical review and citizen science tool selection in Stage 4.

In particular, in this step, all insights generated thus far are combined (i.e. identified challenge and research questions (Table 7), context analysis (Annex 5) and stakeholder analysis (Annex 6). This information is combined and used to generate the case study's Theory of Change and the specification of its Citizen Science activities. This serves the following purposes:

- The Theory of Change complements the earlier challenge analysis by clarifying what changes are envisaged, why and how they are expected to come about. This is detailed in the Impact Assessment Compendium (working document of MICS WP2).
- Citizen Science activities: the topics for citizen activities identified and agreed with the co-design group are defined in detail, so it is clear *what* will be monitored, *when*, *by whom*, *how* (which tools) and, due to the Theory of Change, *why*!

6 Stage 4: Technical review & Citizen Science tool set up

Main objective of this stage:

- Explore and match existing (open source) tools to monitor identified parameters for each monitoring theme

Measure(s) of completion of stage 4:

- Tools and methods have been identified for each monitoring theme and have been approved by scientific experts
- Guidance and training material compiled
- Open Science compliance assured and data management plan in place

Checklist of Actions to be completed during this stage (for instructions, see sections below)

Action	Done
ACTION 17: Please update details of the selected method & tool(s) in the Citizen Science specification table in Annex 7 for each monitoring theme.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 18: Prepare the guidance material for your case study and a link here to the folder that contains it:	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 19: Prepare the data management plan for your case study and a link here to the folder that contain it:	<input type="checkbox"/>

6.1 Selection of tools/apps

This stage serves to finalise the technical set up for the hands-on citizen science activities. Specifically, it serves to check for existing - ideally open source - tools and methods that can be readily used for the monitoring activities during the co-design and summarised in Annex 7. The selection of appropriate tools and methods needs to be guided by experts from the respective scientific discipline, e.g. water quality experts, biologists, etc., to ensure that the selected tool(s) will help the citizen scientists collect data that is valid and fit for purpose. Moreover, the selection of the data collection tool(s) should be accompanied by considerations for how the data will be visualised and made accessible.

A range of sources can be consulted to check for existing tools and apps, such as:

- [FreshWater Watch](#) kit and app can be used for simple chemical, optical and visual tests to collect data on nutrient concentrations, algal blooms, suspended sediment, bank and in-stream vegetation, and hydrological and ecological conditions. There is a mobile app for uploading data, and an online portal where collected data is visualised in real time.
- [SPOTTERON](#) is a smartphone app system (Android and iPhone) for documenting localised and specific sightings. The collected data is edited for evaluation and represented on maps.
- [Scent Toolbox](#): This is a set of smart technologies designed by the H2020 Scent project to engage citizens in environmental monitoring. Using the Scent Toolbox apps, volunteers collect valuable environmental information. For instance, using Scent Explore, citizens can take photos and videos of changes in the environment and with Scent Measure take measurements of soil conditions.
- [Natusfera](#) is one of the largest citizen science platforms in the biodiversity domain. You can create a project on this platform so that citizen scientists can join it and register, organize and share all sorts of biodiversity observations, including photo sharing and location.

- [WeObserve Toolkit](#): This includes a wide range of open access tools developed by WeObserve's partners, i.e. four Citizens Observatories: GROW, SCENT, Ground Truth 2.0 and LANDSENSECitsci.org.

ACTION 17: Please update details of the selected method & tool(s) in the Citizen Science specification table in Annex 7 for each monitoring theme.

6.2 Preparation of training and guidance material

Citizen scientists often have distinctly different backgrounds and affinity with tools and apps and, moreover, they may join at different stages of the monitoring process. Many of the existing tools are already accompanied by guidance material or even fully fledged 'train the trainer' sessions (e.g. the Fresh Water Watch kit).

To ensure the quality of the data collection efforts and to ease onboarding of your citizen scientists, it is good practice to prepare guidance material (e.g. a PDF) for your initiative that summarises the following:

- Context and purpose of the citizen science initiative (i.e. the identified challenge it is addressing)
- Summary of the monitoring scheme
- A 'walk through' text and images for the respective tools and apps
- Contact details of the citizen science initiative lead

Depending on the choice of tool(s), you will need to plan and implement dedicated training sessions.

ACTION 18: Prepare the guidance material for your case study and a link here to the folder that contains it:

Link to folder containing the guidance material for your case study:

6.3 Open Science compliance

The MICS project works under an Open Science paradigm. This means that the data and results of the citizen science activities should be made openly available and accessible, wherever possible and appropriate.

Therefore you need to decide how to implement data management principles to enhance discoverability, accessibility, usability, secure preservation and curation of the data generated by your citizen science initiative. Detailed guidance on how to do this is available on the WeObserve Cookbook page ['I want to work with data ... by managing the data'](#).

ACTION 19: Prepare the data management plan for your case study and a link here to the folder that contain it:

Link to the folder containing the data management plan for your case study:

7 Stage 5: Plan & launch Citizen Science activities

Main objective of this stage:

- Start of the hands-on activities and, ideally, the involvement and reach of a wider audience than those stakeholders involved in the co-design process thus far
- Transition from a co-design group to a Citizen Science community of stakeholders

Measure(s) of completion of stage 5:

- Citizen Science activities are known and available to the public
- First Data collected
- Tailored invitation messages for different target audiences, based on their respective incentives and barriers
- Review of technology performance and adjustments done, if needed
- Frequent Q&A collated and made accessible to new citizen scientists

Details

Depending on the type of Citizen Science activities, their ultimate purpose (ambition identified in stage 1) and their socio-political context (identified in stage 2), a public launch might be appropriate and include a publicity event to raise awareness and recruit new citizen scientists, but also a demonstration to specific political stakeholders etc. In terms of stakeholder engagement, this stage marks the formal launch of the citizen science activities to the wider public, ideally led by community organizers with support from co-design facilitators and technical developers. The following activities need to be undertaken, taking into account whether synergies can be created across different monitoring themes of your case study (identified in Annex 7):

- Definition of target audiences for launch event
- Incentives & Barriers analysis: what enables/hinders participation of citizen scientists (and other stakeholders) in the Citizen Science activities?
- Communication and outreach to mobilize members of the public / target audience
- Launch event(s) organisation & implementation
- Final check of operational data collection tools, technology and visualisation system
- Training of moderators and data collectors
- Monitor/troubleshoot tool/technology performance during launch event

Checklist of Actions to be completed during this stage

Action	Done
ACTION 20: Identify the target audience for the launch event and add their respective incentives/barriers for participation in Annex 2 (last column).	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 21: Complete the planning and reflection tool in Annex 9 to organise the launch events for hands-on Citizen Science activities, taking into account how you can best address the incentives/barriers of the target audience(s).	<input type="checkbox"/>

8 Stage 6: Analysis, outreach & triggering change

Main objective of this stage:

- Analyse the data collected by the citizen scientists
- Prepare and share the results with the citizen scientists and other key stakeholders in line with the agreed objectives of the citizen science activities via suitable outreach mechanisms and awareness raising

Measure(s) of completion of stage 6:

- Results of data analysis ready and approved by relevant scientific expert(s)
- Results visualised; data and results available online as Open Data and Open Access
- Outreach and awareness raising activities planned and implemented

Checklist of Actions to be completed during this stage (for instructions, see sections below)

Action	Done
ACTION 22: Process the collected data and include a link here to the folder that contains the results:	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 23: For the targeted as well as public outreach events that you organise to disseminate and discuss the results, make sure you continue to complete the planning and reflection tool in Annex 8 <u>for each event</u>.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 24: Continue to update the stakeholder management tool in Annex 2.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 25: Consult the Theory of Change in the MICS Impact Assessment Compendium of your case study and discuss with your case study stakeholders who takes what strategic action. Complete the planning and reflection tool in Annex 8 <u>for each event</u>.	<input type="checkbox"/>

8.1 Data analysis and interpretation of results

Depending on the generation of data in terms of timing for each of the specific monitoring theme(s) and research question(s) that your citizen science activities are addressing (as specified in Annex 7), you will need to undertake the data analysis and interpretation at distinctly different moments in time before you can collate them. In any case, as for stage 4 (selection of tools and apps), this stage must be informed and guided by relevant scientific expertise to ensure the quality and validity of results.

Detailed guidance on how to undertake data analysis and interpretation, using relevant (open source) tools and approaches, is available in the WeObserve Cookbook on the following pages:

- [I want to generate insights and results from our data and knowledge by visualising and interpreting the data](#)
- [I want to generate insights and results from our data and knowledge by analysing the data](#)

ACTION 22: Process the collected data and include a link here to the folder that contains the results:

Link to the folder containing results for your case study:

8.2 Outreach and awareness raising activities

A crucial aspect of sound citizen science is to provide the results to, and follow up directly with, the citizen scientists, so that they receive feedback and outputs from the activities they took part in. One way to do so is to make the results available online, e.g. on the website of a participating NGO or on a dedicated online platform (e.g. set up during Stage 4 – Technical review & Citizen Science tool set up).

Moreover, you should share the data as well as the results as per MICS Open Science practice. Guidance on how to share your data as Open Data and making sure your results are available Open Access on global platforms, is available in the WeObserve Cookbook on the following pages:

- [I want to work with data by sharing our data](#)
- [I want to ensure sustainability of the Citizen Observatory after the funding period by making outputs open access](#)

ACTION 23: For the targeted as well as public outreach events that you organise to disseminate and discuss the results, make sure you continue to complete the planning and reflection tool in Annex 8 for each event.

ACTION 24: Continue to update the stakeholder management tool in Annex 2.

8.3 Triggering change

With the results of the monitoring activities available, the required evidence is now in place to follow up with key stakeholders via strategic activities in order to achieve the objectives that had been agreed during the co-design process (as recorded in Table 7) and to trigger the changes stipulated in your Theory of Change via the devised strategies (see Impact Assessment Compendium for your case study).

ACTION 25: Consult the Theory of Change in the MICS Impact Assessment Compendium of your case study and discuss with your case study stakeholders who takes what strategic action. Complete the planning and reflection tool in Annex 8 for each event.

9 Stage 7: Evaluation

Main objective of this stage:

- Obtain clarity on whether activities will be concluded or continued
- Enlarge the community of citizen scientists and other stakeholders (if applicable)
- Update and enhance technical tools (if applicable)

Measure(s) of completion of stage 7:

- Clarification obtained from key stakeholders on intention to continue beyond MICS funded period
- If applicable, sustainability activities have been identified and agreed

Checklist of Actions to be completed during this stage (for instructions, see sections below)

Action	Done
ACTION 26: Organise the ‘sustainability’ meeting and complete the planning and reflection tool in Annex 8 for the event.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 27 (if applicable): Summarise your agreed sustainability actions in Table 8 below.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Details

This stage presents the final part of the co-design process and concerns the go/no go decision of the MICS case study stakeholders to continue their activities beyond the funded project period (December 2021).

A key aspect is that ‘failing to plan is planning to fail’. Therefore, a timely ‘sustainability’ meeting (online or F2F) should be facilitated by the MICS case study team with the key stakeholders of the case study (citizen scientists, local authorities, scientists, MICS teams members, etc.) to decide whether the activities are complete or whether there is a need to continue and/or even expand their activities and collaboration beyond 2021, transitioning from the initial MICS case study to continuous operation of citizen science activities.

ACTION 26: Organise the ‘sustainability’ meeting and complete the planning and reflection tool in Annex 8 for the event.

If the outcome of the ‘sustainability’ meeting is that the citizen science activities will continue beyond 2021, concrete actions should be identified and agree upon to ensure the sustainability of the citizen science activities. While doing so, take stock of the initial experiences that the citizen scientists had while using the data collection tools (and platform), as well as problems and issues reported, so that fixes, adjustments and additions to functionality can be included in the Action Plan.

Inspiration on different ways for ensuring the sustainability of citizen science activities is available in the WeObserve Cookbook on the following pages:

- [I want to ensure sustainability of the Citizen Observatory after the funding period by accessing open funding calls](#)
- [I want to ensure sustainability of the Citizen Observatory after the funding period by collaborating with other Citizen Observatories that have similar objectives](#)

ACTION 27 (if applicable): Summarise your agreed sustainability actions in Table 8 below.

Table 8: Summary of agreed sustainability actions

Action description	Who	Potential resources	Due date

If desired, the stages outlined in this co-design process can be applied in an iterative fashion: upon completion of a given campaign, start again with stage 1 to check for changes in the context and stakeholder composition.

References

Alfonso, L., Mazzoleni, M., Pfeiffer, E., Wehn, U. (2017) Functional design, Ground Truth 2.0 deliverable D1.5, September.

Anema, K., Pfeiffer, E. and Wehn, U. (2018) Updated Engagement Strategy, Ground Truth 2.0 deliverable D1.4, April.

Pfeiffer, E., Wehn, U. and Anema, K. (2018) Updated Stakeholder analysis of the Demonstration Cases, Ground Truth 2.0 deliverable D1.2, February.

Wehn, U. (2019) WP4 Co design of Citizen Science activities in the MICS case studies, MICS F2F plenary meeting, 15-17 July, Bucharest.

Wehn, U., and Pfeiffer, E. (2020) Guidelines for Citizen Observatories and Future Recommendations, Ground Truth 2.0 deliverable D1.13, February.

MICS deliverables

Ceccaroni, L. & Williams, C. (2019). D1.2: Project Management Handbook. *Deliverable report of project H2020 MICS (grant agreement No 824711)*.

Wehn, U., Williams, C. & Ceccaroni, L. (2019). D6.1: Ethics H - Requirement No. 1. *Deliverable report of project H2020 MICS (grant agreement No 824711)*.

Williams, C., Wehn, U. & Ceccaroni, L. (2019). D6.2: Ethics POPD - Requirement No. 2. *Deliverable report of project H2020 MICS (grant agreement No 824711)*.

Annex 1 – Monitoring & evaluation

The MICS Impact Assessment Framework developed by WP2 will assess the evolving impacts of the MICS case studies as a distinct effort, with separate instructions for the case studies.

As part of scoping the ambition of your case study, it is important to define the envisaged timing of each stage of the citizen science co-design process to measure progress. This will provide continuous means for monitoring & evaluation of your case study in terms of progress through the citizen science co-design process and implementation of citizen science activities and to capture lessons learned from the application of the co-design methodology.

	Stage 1 Getting started: Rapid screening & Stage 2 Tailor methods to context	Stage 3 Initiate co-design group & capture requirements	Stage 4 Technical review & citizen science tool set up	Stage 5 Plan & launch Citizen Science activities	Stage 6 Analysis, outreach & triggering change	Stage 7 Enhance & sustain citizen science tools and activities
Planned completion of activities						
Actual completion of activities						
Comments/explanation						
Lessons learned						

Annex 3 – Co-design events - Interaction Logbooks

On this page, please complete the summary information in the table below per co-design event to create a cumulative overview of all events held for the co-design of the Citizen Science activities in your case study.

Logbook entry #	Date	Title of event	Location
1			
2			

Copy the logbook table on the next page for each event and complete one per co-design event

Logbook entry #1	
Event Information	
Title of the event	
Date	
Location of the event	
MICS facilitation team (names, organisations, roles)	
Stakeholder attendees	
Structure of the event	<i>e.g. presentation given, workshops run, etc.</i>
Objectives of the event	
Methods/tools used	
Event evaluation results	
Feedback from participating stakeholders via event evaluation form	
Team observations and assessment (MICS team feedback)	
Were the objectives of the event achieved?	
Physical environment	
Participants	
Competencies	
Interactions	
Direct quotes	
Pros about the event	

Cons about the event	
Lessons learned	
Notes for following activities	
Goals for the next Interaction Moment	
Required actions	
Required support from MICS partners	

Annex 4 – Co-design session – session structure

Session item	Purpose	Desired output/ understanding	Who	Materials, support	Timing
Welcome and introduction	<p><i>Introduce the MICS project</i></p> <p><i>Explain context (NBS and citizen science)</i></p> <p><i>Objective of the workshop</i></p>	Awareness of project context, scope	<i>Facilitator</i>	<i>Slides</i>	<i>10 min.</i>
Participants' expectations	<p><i>Warm up using post its, writing stuff down; capture their expectations on post its</i></p> <p><i>[If many participants, do this per table/group then report back citizen science stakeholder categories only)</i></p>	Ensure everyone knows who's in the room (per stakeholder triangle) and what the respective expectations are; basis for managing expectations over time	<i>Participants</i>	<i>Post its, wall space</i>	<i>15 min.</i>
Structure, envisaged results & approach	<i>Provide clarity on structure of this workshop (pyramid) and overall purpose/envisaged results</i>	Awareness of the way of working in this workshop/project and timelines	<i>Facilitator</i>	<i>Slide</i>	<i>5 min.</i>
The local story	<i>The local NBS (rationale, plans, progress)</i>	Awareness of local NBS history and rationale	<i>Facilitator, Interactive discussion</i>	<i>Flip-chart</i>	<i>15 min.</i>
Identifying the issue	<p><i>What problem does the NBS address?</i></p> <p><i>Individually: answer using post its</i></p>	Multi-stakeholder perspective gathered on the problem and its manifestations/consequences; joint definition and agreement of the issue	<i>Interactive discussion</i>	<i>Post its</i>	<i>15 min.</i>

Session item	Purpose	Desired output/ understanding	Who	Materials, support	Timing
How does this problem manifest itself in your daily lives?	<p><i>Identify manifestations of the problem</i></p> <p><i>Place the post-it notes on the sustainability compass poster and check if everything is there.</i></p> <p><i>Make additional ones if necessary</i></p> <p><i>Indication of trend per indicator</i></p>	<p>Structured categorisation of consequences</p> <p>Trend identification per indicator</p>	<i>Participants</i>	<p><i>Cards and Compass poster</i></p> <p><i>Post-it notes</i></p>	<i>20 min.</i>
	<p>What is happening?</p> <p><i>Coffee break</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>All take a look at the connection-maps of the other groups.</i> • <i>Discuss with them and add insights where relevant</i> <p><i>Brief plenary feedback & discussion on wording of central challenge</i></p>	<p>Identify commonalities/differences/additions</p> <p>Agreed central challenge addressed by the NBS</p>	<i>Participants</i>		<i>10 min.</i>
Why is it happening?	<p><i>In small groups (3 people max) try to find</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Patterns</i> - <i>Causal relations</i> - <i>Feedback loops</i> <p><i>between the different post-it notes and indicate connections.</i></p>	<p>Causal analysis (relationships between cause & effect)</p> <p>Connection map</p>	<i>Participants</i>	<p><i>Markers</i></p> <p><i>Additional post-it notes</i></p>	<i>20 min.</i>
	<p><i>Visualize the relationships found by all groups on the wall – Caroussel; place comments on post-it notes</i></p>	<p>Joint causal analysis & trend identification</p>	<i>Participants</i>	<p><i>Markers</i></p> <p><i>Additional post-it notes</i></p>	<i>10 min</i>

Session item	Purpose	Desired output/ understanding	Who	Materials, support	Timing
What can I do/ what can we do	<p><i>Introduce spheres of influence and discuss personal actions.</i></p> <p><i>Post-its to indicate own influence</i></p> <p><i>Bridge: Together we can do even more</i></p> <p><i>What aspects can be influenced – first in general and then by whom? How?</i></p>	<p>Awareness of participants' own role & influence</p> <p>Identification of leverage points</p>	<i>Facilitator & Participants</i>	<p><i>Slide</i></p> <p><i>WeObserve MOOC trailer</i></p> <p><i>Post its</i></p>	<i>5 min.</i>
How does Citizen Science work	<p><i>Monitoring, communicating (dialogue between neighbours or with authorities)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Select specific leverage points that citizen science can address</i> <p><i>Possible roles in citizen science</i></p>	<p>Illustration of citizen science from another group to indicate monitoring and communication elements and their use</p>	<i>Facilitator</i>	<i>Slides</i>	<i>5 min.</i>
How will Citizen Science address the problem?	<p><i>What should we be measuring and communicating about?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Key research questions/data needs</i> - <i>Stress importance of involving the right actors</i> <p><i>Inventorise what they already monitor/measure, what data exists already, etc.</i></p>	<p>Short presentations per group to indicate where/how monitoring and communication will be of use and how</p>	<p><i>Participants</i></p> <p><i>Facilitators to write along on flip chart</i></p>	<p><i>Group material</i></p> <p><i>Flip chart</i></p>	<i>20 min.</i>
Let's do it!	<p><i>Objectives of their citizen science activities</i></p> <p><i>Devising SMART objectives for the citizen science activities</i></p>	<p>Objective of the citizen science activities formulated & agreed</p>	<i>Participants</i>	<i>Post its</i>	<i>15 min.</i>

Session item	Purpose	Desired output/ understanding	Who	Materials, support	Timing
	<p><i>Individually:</i> Write down suggested objective of the citizen science (1 objective per post-it)</p> <p>Brief plenary discussion on suggestions</p>				
Closing	<p><i>Summarise citizen science activities & objectives</i></p> <p><i>Solicit personal pledges & commitment</i></p>	<p>Clarity on citizen science purpose and scope</p> <p>Commit for next meeting: co-design of tools for identified monitoring scheme</p>	<p><i>Facilitator & participants</i></p>	<p><i>Slides & Flipchart</i></p>	<p><i>15 min.</i></p>

Annex 5 – Context Analysis

Case Boundaries:	Case study responses
<p>“You have ‘placed your case study on a map’: It will take place in [...]. How was the location for the case study chosen? For example, does it match a political or administrative entity? Or a geographical or natural area?”</p>	
<p>Political/Administrative Boundaries</p>	
<p>“Does your case involve cross-jurisdictional institutions (e.g. basin organizations, nature reserves,...)? “</p>	
<p>“Your case study will be affected by a range of laws and regulations. How many levels of government does your country have (e.g. local, district, provincial, national, EU)? Which level(s) of government set or implement policies on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the issue? • citizens’ rights to information and participation? 	
<p>Political process mapping: “Who “owns” or coordinates the decision making process your citizen science activities link to? Who has the legal authority to decide, who can be ordered to contribute, who has a formal right to participate, who is usually asked to advise?”</p>	
<p>“Who controls what can be discussed in formal decision making processes [related to the issue of your case study]? Are there public channels to raise issues or comment, or is access to policy debates restricted? Do you need to observe formal rules or understand technical or political language to contribute?”</p>	

Environmental Boundaries	
“Your citizen science activities will collect data on environmental issues. Often, such issues ‘know no boundaries’ – i.e. both problems and solutions involve actors ‘somewhere else’. Does your case collect data on phenomena with ‘natural borders’? Think e.g. about rivers (catchments), region-external sources of pollution, distinct ecosystems or habitats, or migratory species?”	
Social Boundaries	
“People are social creatures. We identify as members of groups and communities. If you asked people in your region to describe themselves would they identify [by nationality, the region, the city]? Is the population homogenous, or are there major ethnic or tribal groups, different languages, or religious, social or cultural sub-groups?”	
“Which places are role models for your region? E.g., do policy-makers frequently copy programs from or compare themselves to other cities/regions? Which cities/regions are watched as cultural centres and trendsetters?”	
Economic Boundaries	
“Economic power is a major driver of all policy. How is economic power distributed in your case study area? Are there major employers or concentrated industrial clusters, ports or special economic zones inside or outside the project area?”	
Technical Boundaries	
“The MICS citizen science activities will need to be compatible with the way people use technology in your case region. Can you think of any specific,	

<p>positive or negative aspects of the technical tools in your case study (e.g. unequal network access)? Are there any particular local preferences for social media networks you know of? Are there any popular local online communities?”</p>	
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Annex 6 – Stakeholder Analysis

	Stakeholder	Role	Interest	Topic	Category	Interest (H/M/L)	Influence (H/M/L)	Support Profile	Personal Notes
1									
2									
3									
4									

Annex 7 – Citizen Science activities specification

Instruction: for each monitoring theme identified during the co-design process, below please list the research question(s) (see Table 7) and specify the 'citizen-science'-based data collection process.

Note: the content of column 'Method' will be further refined and finalised during Stage 4 'Technical review & Citizen Science tool set up'.

Monitoring theme	Research question	Data collection				
		Parameter(s) to be observed (what)	Method (how)	Frequency of observation (how often)	Observer(s) (by whom)	Location(s) (where)

Annex 8 – Events planning & reflection [[launch/hands-on citizen science/outreach](#)]

1. On this page, please complete the summary information in the table below per Citizen Science launch/hands-on citizen science/outreach event to create a cumulative overview of all events held for the launch and outreach regarding the Citizen Science activities in your case study.

Logbook entry #	Date	Title of event	Location
1			
2			
3			
...			

2. Copy the logbook table on the next page for each Citizen Science launch/hands-on citizen science/outreach event and complete one per event

Citizen Science activities - Event Information – Fill during Event Planning	
Title of the Event	
Date	
Location	
Objectives of the event (from MICS case study perspective)	
Organizer	<i>[Does the MICS case study team organize the event itself or does the launch take place as part of another event? In the latter case, please briefly describe the organizer and the nature and purpose of the main event.]</i>
How would you characterize the planned event?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Hands-on Citizen Science event (= the goal is that as many people as possible <u>actively participate</u> in the MICS case study citizen science activities) If yes, What monitoring theme(s) (from Annex 6) were addressed: Who was the target audience? <input type="checkbox"/> the broader public, directly <input type="checkbox"/> the press and/or local multipliers <input type="checkbox"/> other:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Publicity Event (= the goal is that as many people as possible <u>learn about</u> the MICS case study citizen science activities) If yes, who was the target audience? <input type="checkbox"/> the broader public, directly <input type="checkbox"/> the press and/or local multipliers <input type="checkbox"/> others:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Recruitment Event (= a specific target audience is invited/ presented to, with the goal to increase membership, reach or impact of the MICS case study citizen science activities) If yes, who was the target audience? <input type="checkbox"/> Citizens <input type="checkbox"/> Policy Makers <input type="checkbox"/> other:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Issue-Driven Event (= the event is focused on the core issue of the MICS case study, the citizen science activities are only indirectly promoted)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Internal Event (= kick-off event aimed at galvanizing citizen science Community members and signal that ‘we are up and running’)</p> <p>Comments:</p>
Do you have specific targets for the launch event?	<i>[e.g. number of volunteers signed up, observations submitted, press mentions generated, specific persons have been successfully</i>

	<i>approached]</i>
Event materials to prepare/produced	
Materials <i>(please tick relevant boxes)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Poster/Flyer/Programme <input type="checkbox"/> Photographs <input type="checkbox"/> Presentation <input type="checkbox"/> Participant Feedback/Survey/Evaluation/CO sign up <input type="checkbox"/> Other outputs produced by participants <input type="checkbox"/> Press articles <input type="checkbox"/> Minutes/Report
	<input type="checkbox"/> Copies of materials produced have been stored in the MICS case study folder
Observations by project team/facilitators:	
Facilitators and attending MICS team members <i>[all persons named should contribute to this protocol]</i>	
Physical environment <i>[Notes regarding the event space, ability to engage with stakeholders, visibility of the MICS case study if the launch was part of a bigger event, traffic, noise levels etc.]</i>	
Participants <i>[Notes regarding the configuration of stakeholders, e.g. number and type of stakeholders, age and gender mix. Did attendance meet your expectations? Were they the right stakeholders to achieve the event goals (as outlined above)?]</i>	
Were the objectives & targets of the event achieved <i>(as outlined above)?</i>	

<p>Recruitment <i>[If the launch was a recruitment event, how was the recruitment conducted (e.g. signing up sheet)? How many and what type of stakeholders were recruited?]</i></p>	
<p>Competencies <i>[Ability of participants to grasp the purpose and approach of the observatory? Ability of participants to use the pilot platform? Which aspects, features or tools caused problems or required a lot of explanation?]</i></p>	
<p>Feedback and Interactions <i>[Notes regarding the reaction and attitudes of participants. How was the idea of the MICS case study citizen science activities received? What was the focus of questions and comments? Expressions of conflicts and support, including nonverbal behaviour?]</i></p>	
<p>Q&A of (technical) issues encountered & addressed <i>[Note typical issues encountered and how they were addressed]</i></p>	
<p>Memorable quotes <i>[Made by whom? Why was it noteworthy?]</i></p>	
<p>Summary assessment of the launch event</p>	
<p>Quality of the Co-Design <i>[Based on the interactions with 'new' stakeholders in during the event, do you feel the co-design process successfully captured what is relevant for people in the area?]</i></p>	
<p>Pros about the event</p>	<p>Open to everyone, outdoor activity</p>

Cons about the event	Linked to the MICS case study ambition, but needs to be explained
Lessons learnt <i>[e.g. regarding the format, content, or assumptions made in the planning]</i>	
Will there be additional events? If yes, add notes/inputs for future events at the site	

Annex 9 – Case study team minutes

For each case study team teleconference, copy the generic structure for team minutes below and complete

Date, time:

Attendance:

Agenda:

Action Points from last meeting:

Minutes:

Action Points for next meeting: